

1 **Front-of-pack labels and young consumers: An experimental investigation of nutrition and**
2 **sustainability claims in Chile**

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4 **Author names and affiliations**

5 Gabriela Fretes, PhD^{a,d*}, Norbert L.W. Wilson, PhD^b, Camila Corvalan, MPH MD PhD^c,
6 Christina D. Economos, PhD^d, Sean B. Cash, PhD^d

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8 ^a International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI), 1201 Eye St NW, Washington, DC, USA
9 20005-3915, G.Fretes@cgiar.org

10 ^b Duke Divinity School, Sanford School of Public Policy, and World Food Policy Center, Duke
11 University, 407 Chapel Drive, Durham, NC, USA 27708-0968, nwilson@div.duke.edu

12 ^c Instituto de Nutrición y Tecnología de los Alimentos (INTA), Universidad de Chile, Santiago,
13 Chile 7830489, ccorvalan@inta.uchile.cl

14 ^d Friedman School of Nutrition Science and Policy, Tufts University, 150 Harrison Avenue,
15 Boston, MA, USA 02111, christina.economos@tufts.edu, sean.cash@tufts.edu

16

17 ***Corresponding author:** Gabriela Fretes, G.Fretes@cgiar.org

18 International Food Policy Research Institute (IFPRI), 1201 Eye St NW, Washington, DC, USA
19 20005-3915

Abbreviations¹

¹ LFLA: Law of Food Labeling and Advertising; FOP: Front-of-package; DCE: discrete choice experiment; FECHIC: Food Environment Chilean Cohort; GOCS: Growth Obesity Cohort Study; INTA: Institute of Nutrition and Food Technology; SBER: Social, Behavioral and Education Research; MNL: Multinomial Logit; RUT: Random Utility Theory; IID: Independent and Identically Distributed; IIA: Independence of Irrelevant Alternatives; AIC: Akaike Information Criterion; BIC: Bayesian Information Criterion; CAIC: Consistent Akaike Information Criterion

20 **Front-of-pack labels and young consumers: An experimental investigation of nutrition and**
21 **sustainability claims in Chile**

22 **Abstract**

23 A better understanding of youth as autonomous consumers in the food market is needed to guide
24 food and nutrition policies to achieve healthier and sustainable diets because they interact with
25 the food environment to obtain, prepare, and consume food and beverages. Compared to other
26 age groups, evidence on children and adolescents (youth) purchasing behavior and front-of-
27 package (FOP) labeling is limited. The objective of the study was to assess youth's purchasing
28 behavior by conducting an online discrete choice experiment (DCE) in Santiago, Chile. We
29 assessed four different food attributes: price, FOP nutrition warning label, FOP eco-label, and
30 type of product (i.e., yogurt, cookie, apple). Data were analyzed using mixed logit models
31 complemented with latent class logit models to further explore heterogeneity in preferences. A
32 total of 329 youth aged 10-14 years participated in the study. Our results reveal that youths'
33 purchasing behavior is mostly determined by price, followed by product type and environmental
34 sustainability as measured by the FOP eco-label; responsiveness to price was not moderated by
35 whether the youth received pocket money from a family member regularly. We further identified
36 five classes (groups) of youth consumers where some exhibited preference for health and
37 nutrition attributes, environmental sustainability, or price. Our findings provide a better
38 understanding of youth as diverse and autonomous consumers and suggest at least some youths
39 are responsive to labeling interventions.

40

41 **Keywords:** discrete choice experiment, children, consumer behavior, eco-labels, warning labels.

42 **1. Introduction**

43 Promoting healthy and sustainable diets through increased availability and affordability of
44 nutritious foods is essential for youth growth and development (Hollis et al., 2020). While it has
45 been recognized that the food environment and other elements of the food system can influence
46 people's food choices, children and adolescents (youth from hereafter) as decision-makers play
47 an important role in demanding nutritious foods to achieve healthier and more sustainable diets
48 because they interact with the food environment at multiple scales (Sharma & Sonwaney, 2014).
49 As a result, attention is needed to study food choices in young consumers by focusing on
50 purchasing behavior because habits and behaviors developed during childhood can persist in
51 later stages of life (Scaglioni et al., 2018). McNeal describes children as a three-in-one-market as
52 they are current consumers that spend their own money at school kiosks and corner stores
53 (primary market), they are influencers at home where they can demand healthier foods (influence
54 market), and they are future consumers (future market) (McNeal, 1992). Similarly, adolescents,
55 with greater autonomy than younger children, purchase foods based on their knowledge and
56 preferences (Fox & Timmer, 2020).

57 A rich literature on consumer research assesses food choices in adults in different contexts, yet
58 few studies have investigated youth as autonomous consumers in the food market (Cash et al.,
59 2017; Hartmann et al, 2017; Landwehr et al., 2023). Youth have considerable autonomous
60 spending power for foods, with snacks representing a large share of the foods purchased (Cash et
61 al., 2017; Dennisuk et al., 2011; Lyerly et al., 2017; Shin et al., 2015). A study conducted using
62 an experimental framework in Boston, USA with 8-11-year-old children found that children's
63 snack choices were predominantly determined by product type, followed by brand and price
64 (Hartmann et al, 2017). An interesting finding was that children who received an allowance were

65 more sensitive to price than those who did not (Hartmann et al., 2017), which can be associated
66 with having better budgeting skills. A recent study conducted in Germany with children aged 7-
67 10 years found that price responsiveness is influenced by cognitive ability and age (Landwehr et
68 al., 2023).

69 Although researchers have documented that youth's main driver of snack choice is taste (Fretes
70 et al., 2021; Letona et al., 2014; Marty et al., 2018), research documenting the influence of youth
71 food literacy on purchase decisions is lacking. Vidgen and Gallegos define food literacy as "the
72 scaffolding that empowers individuals, households, communities, or nations to protect diet
73 quality through change and strengthen dietary resilience over time. It is composed of a collection
74 of inter-related knowledge, skills and behaviors required to plan, manage, select, prepare, and eat
75 food to meet needs and determine intake" (Vidgen & Gallegos, 2014). Being more food literate
76 early in life can provide youth with skills to improve their food choices and practices as adult
77 consumers. While experts argue there is not yet a universally accepted tool to assess food literacy
78 in youth (Carroll et al., 2021), the multidimensional tool proposed by Amin et al. (2019) is a
79 valid, reliable, and feasible instrument to measure different children's food literacy domains such
80 as cooking skills, nutrition knowledge, food systems knowledge as well as self-efficacy skills to
81 make healthier food choices (Amin et al., 2019; Lehnerd, 2018). Here, we adapt a portion of this
82 scale for use in helping to further understand differences in youth's choices.

83 Improving consumer behavior through better and more informed food choices is key to
84 achieving healthy and sustainable diets. In the past years, the food industry has started to include
85 eco-labels on food products highlighting different sustainability attributes such as organic,
86 environmentally friendly, and farm-raised. Consumer responses to these different eco-labels have
87 been studied in adults with conflicting results. Some studies suggest that eco-labels are

88 associated with more sustainable food choices (Potter et al., 2021). Other studies, however, find
89 that the level of understanding of the sustainability concept, as well as the use of eco-labels, is
90 low and does not influence food choice (Annunziata et al., 2019; Grunert et al., 2014; van Bussel
91 et al., 2022). Little is known, however, about youth's food choices linked to the presence of eco-
92 labels or environmental sustainability. A qualitative study in Chile found that children 8-9 years
93 old understood the concept of sustainability in food when it was communicated in plain language
94 and a simple eco-label may be an effective tool for more sustainable food choices (Fretes et al.,
95 2021).

96 To date, only a few studies assessed the interacting effects of different food attributes in youth's
97 purchase decisions in a discrete choice experimental framework (Hartmann et al., 2017; Michaels-
98 Igbokwe et al., 2021; Landwehr et al., 2023), and no experimental study has been conducted in
99 youth outside of the U.S, Canada and Germany (Cash et al., 2017; Hartmann et al., 2017; Landwehr
100 et al., 2023) nor has focused on environmental sustainability attributes. Our setting for this study
101 is Chile. Recently, the country implemented the Law of Food Labeling and Advertising (LFLA),
102 with warning nutrition front-of-package labels in packaged foods and a voluntary eco-label that
103 provides information about the recyclability of food packages (Corvalan et al., 2019; Ministerio
104 de Ambiente de Chile, 2022a; Ministerio de Ambiente de Chile, 2022b). The LFLA has three main
105 components: (1) mandatory front-of-package (FOP) warning labels on packaged foods, (2)
106 restrictions on child-directed marketing of foods with FOP warning labels (children <14 years),
107 and (3) school regulations (foods with FOP warning labels cannot be sold, distributed, or marketed
108 in schools). The law was implemented in three phases beginning in June 2016; other countries in
109 the Latin American region such as Argentina, Colombia, Mexico, Peru, and Uruguay followed
110 with similar FOP warning label regulations. Directive FOP labeling has been proposed as a

111 strategy to reduce the complexity of decision-making in food environments by communicating
112 readily accessible information to consumers in a uniform and predictable manner, ideally to guide
113 healthier food choices at the point of purchase. Studies conducted with youth in Brazil, Chile,
114 Uruguay, and Mexico suggest that label design can influence their perceptions of food products
115 and impact their food choices (Ares et al., 2016; Arrua et al., 2017; Lima et al., 2018; Hammond
116 et al., 2023). Youth seem to better understand the information communicated through warning
117 labels compared to other systems such as the Traffic Lights, Health Star Ratings and Guideline
118 Daily Amount (GDA) systems (Hammond et al., 2023; Arrua et al., 2017; Lima et al., 2018). FOP
119 labeling policies not only drive consumer behavior changes, but also industry behavior changes
120 along the food supply chain by incentivizing product reformulation (Reyes et al., 2020). Thus, the
121 Chilean context provides an important opportunity to study youth's behavior in the food market in
122 an evolving policy environment.

123 The objective of the present study is to assess Chilean youth's purchasing behavior by eliciting
124 their preferences for snacks. Furthermore, this study explores how different food attributes
125 influence youths' purchasing decisions, considering their individual characteristics. By
126 examining the heterogeneity in preferences in different groups of youth, we can better
127 understand their purchasing behavior and identify potential interventions targeted to the different
128 segments. We conducted an online discrete choice experiment (DCE) to assess food attributes
129 (i.e., product type, nutrition FOP warning label, price, eco-label) that shape snack choice. We
130 hypothesize that: (H1) The presence of the (1a) FOP warning label and (1b) eco-label changes
131 the likelihood of choosing a snack, (H2) Price affects youth's demand for snack foods, and (H3)
132 Higher food literacy scores (food system domain) change the likelihood of choosing a snack with
133 an eco-label. H1 and H2 were drawn from the literature on adult responses to warning labels

134 and/or price and were also key themes that were elicited in previous qualitative work (Fretes et
135 al., 2021). H3 was posed to assess food literacy (specifically, in the food systems domain) as a
136 driver of environmental sustainability among youth and their preference (or not) for eco-labels as
137 a proxy to identify environmentally conscious consumers. This study aims to better understand
138 youth as both current and future consumers in the context of the LFLA and provide a baseline for
139 future research. Insights provided by this research are important for understanding the influence
140 of both policy (e.g., front-of-package nutrition labeling, eco-labeling) and youth's food literacy
141 on food choices and purchase decisions.

142

143 **2. Methods**

144 *2.1 Participants*

145 To study youth's food choices, we recruited a purposive sub-sample of children and adolescents
146 aged 10-14 who were siblings of participants from two ongoing cohort studies: the Food
147 Environment Chilean Cohort (FECHIC) and Growth Obesity Cohort Study (GOCS) (Jensen et
148 al., 2019; Rebolledo et al., 2019). Participants in both cohort studies are from low- and middle-
149 income families from the southeastern area of Santiago, Chile. Recruitment of the sub-sample
150 was facilitated through collaboration with researchers at the University of Chile.

151 Potential participants were screened to ensure they met the inclusion criteria: being a sibling of
152 participants from the FECHIC or GOCS cohort studies and being 10-14 years old at the time of
153 recruitment. Participants who were not able to use a mobile device (i.e., cellphone, computer,
154 laptop) for any reason were excluded. To recruit youth, their parents were invited to participate
155 in the study through phone calls and emails. Interested individuals received the online survey
156 link and were asked to complete the survey within two weeks of the date they received the email.

157 We sent two email reminders, one at two weeks and another at three weeks to facilitate
158 participation. At the beginning of the online survey, parents were informed about the objective of
159 the study, potential benefits, potential risks, and the voluntary nature of the study. We obtained
160 parental informed consent and child assent before data collection. Parental informed consent
161 took place when parents signed the online forms located at the beginning of the online survey. If
162 parents signed the consent form, the assent form appeared next. Parents were provided with
163 instructions to read the assent form to their youth and ask them for their assent by signing the
164 online form with their names, indicating their voluntary participation. The final sample of
165 participants was 329 youth who were siblings of participants of FECHIC and GOCS. Data were
166 collected online between June and September 2021. Participants received \$5000 Chilean pesos
167 (\approx USD 6) gift cards via email as compensation upon completion of the survey.

168 *2.2 Survey design and data collection*

169 This research used a mixed methods approach, involving qualitative and quantitative methods to
170 evaluate children's and adolescents' purchasing behavior and snack food choices. The protocol
171 for this study was approved by the Ethics Committee of the Institute of Nutrition and Food
172 Technology (INTA) at the University of Chile and the Tufts Social, Behavioral, and Educational
173 Research (SBER) Institutional Review Board.

174 To inform the design of valid choice sets for the online DCE and to guarantee that our survey
175 instrument was age-appropriate and suited to address the research questions, we first conducted
176 eight focus group discussions in a different sample of children (n=30). The aim of the qualitative
177 part of the study was to (a) collect information about children's perceptions of food, nutrition,
178 and environmental sustainability in the Chilean context, and (b) elicit food attributes and
179 attribute levels to be included in the choice experiment. The careful pre-testing of attributes and

180 attribute levels to include in the DCE is a strength of our experimental design because it
181 informed us about the main food attributes generally accepted by children. The pre-testing
182 provided clarity about what each attribute meant for children and the measurement of the
183 attribute levels to minimize the unobserved sources of influence on youth food choices. The
184 qualitative results associated with the first sub-aim are reported in detail elsewhere (Fretes et al.,
185 2021). Specific to the design of the experiment, four attributes were pretested with 30 children:
186 nutrition FOP warning labels, eco-labels, price, and type of food product. Results showed that
187 children had a positive perception of eco-labels and were aware of the nutrition FOP warning
188 labels present in the Chilean market. We also identified children's favorite snack products and
189 asked how much they would pay for each product to inform the price categories for the
190 experiment. Among the favorite snacks were fruit, cookies, and yogurt. In addition to the focus
191 group discussions conducted in July 2020, we conducted one-on-one online interviews with a
192 different sample of children (n=12) in April 2021 to test if the purchase choice task was
193 understood. The focus group discussions and survey pre-test confirmed our quantitative study
194 design, and our stimuli were appropriate.

195 The quantitative part consisted of an online survey delivered via Qualtrics Survey Software
196 (Qualtrics) with two sections: (1) a discrete choice experiment to elicit children's and
197 adolescents' preferences over included food attributes and, (2) a survey regarding children's and
198 adolescents' food literacy, pocket money and demographics. First, youth participated in a DCE
199 (section 1) where they were presented with choice sets (Figure 1) containing two hypothetical
200 snack alternatives (A and B) and a "no purchase" option. The "no purchase" option allowed
201 participants to opt out for any reason. Including this option reduces bias by not forcing
202 participants to choose a product that they may not choose in a real situation. The unit of purchase

203 was a snack available in the Chilean market that represented a combination of attributes
204 (characteristics). The advantage of using choice experiments with children is that after we
205 present a set of food product choice alternatives, product attribute preferences can be revealed
206 without asking participants about their subjective valuation of each specific product attribute
207 under study. Children simply choose the preferred product, and this process allows attribute
208 preferences to be revealed. This method reduces social desirability bias and other upward biases
209 such as the spotlight effect because it does not highlight one attribute or product over other
210 options. Snacks differed by kind of product (i.e., sugared cookies, apple, or flavored yogurt),
211 price (i.e., \$400, \$500, \$600, or \$800 Chilean pesos), presence of nutrition FOP warning labels
212 (i.e., three labels noting “high in calories”, “high in sugars” and “high in saturated fats”, one
213 label indicating “high in sugars” and no label) and presence of an eco-label (i.e., yes or no). For
214 reference, USD 1 was \approx \$800 Chilean pesos when the data were collected. The attributes and
215 attribute levels were chosen based on results from focus group discussions (Fretes et al., 2021)
216 and survey pre-testing (Table 1). In the case of warning labels, we included three labels, one
217 label and no label since focus group participants were able to identify foods with more labels as
218 less healthy and vice versa (i.e., the distinction was clear between three and one label).

219 A full factorial design, even after excluding non-informative combinations ($n=2,556$) would not
220 be practical here, or in most cases, because of the significant cognitive burden that participants
221 are exposed to when presented with all possible combinations (Hensher et al., 2005). Therefore,
222 considering the attributes and attribute levels chosen, a fractional factorial D-optimal choice
223 experimental design was generated using JMP Pro version 14 (JMP®, Version 14). Fractional
224 factorial designs use only a random fraction of all possible combinations. Given that fruits would
225 not receive a FOP nutrition warning label because the LFLA applies only to packaged products,

226 we included a restriction in the design so that apples were free of FOP nutrition warning labels.
227 Similar to previous studies (e.g., Hartmann et al., 2017; Landwehr et al., 2023), our design
228 consisted of 8 choice sets per child to consider children’s limited attention span and avoid
229 fatigue.

230 To facilitate comprehension of the choice task and minimize hypothetical biases, prior to the
231 beginning of the DCE, youth were provided a scenario to contextualize choice (i.e., imagining
232 themselves being at a school kiosk or corner store and wanting to buy a snack). Images of
233 product packages included in the DCE were manipulated from images of products available in
234 Chilean supermarkets in that they only differed concerning those attributes we wanted to
235 investigate, such as nutrition FOP warning labels and/or eco-labels. For example, we
236 manipulated the image of a yogurt that originally did not have warning labels so that it includes
237 one warning label (Figure 2).

238 Following the DCE, youth completed a food literacy survey (section 2). The purpose of
239 conducting the food literacy survey was to explore potential interactions between youth’s food
240 literacy level (specifically, in the food system domain) and the likelihood of choosing a snack
241 with either a FOP nutrition warning label or a FOP eco-label. We used a food literacy survey
242 validated by Amin et al. (2019) with children in the USA. We translated the survey into Spanish,
243 and adapted some sections to include, for example, the warning labels on Chilean food packages.
244 The survey included 34 questions covering five domains: food systems knowledge, cooking
245 skills, cooking knowledge, nutrition knowledge and self-efficacy regarding eating. Although the
246 food systems domain was our primary interest, we also collected information on all the domains
247 included in the survey for descriptive purposes. Participants could achieve a total maximum
248 score of 40 points, with each correct answer contributing to this score. We derived a total score

249 based on participants' performance and estimated participants' performance in each domain. The
250 maximum score for each domain was as follows: food systems knowledge = 12 points, cooking
251 skills = 3 points, cooking knowledge = 6 points, nutrition knowledge = 15 points, and self-
252 efficacy = 4 points. Food literacy domain-specific Cronbach α values were generated to assess
253 internal consistency of each domain, and indicated modest reliability of the translated food
254 systems knowledge domain (food systems knowledge: $\alpha = 0.60$; cooking skills: $\alpha = 0.47$;
255 cooking knowledge: $\alpha = 0.26$; nutrition knowledge: $\alpha = 0.39$; self-efficacy: $\alpha = 0.66$) (Table S3).
256 Survey validation through cognitive interviews was conducted in the sample of children (n=12)
257 that participated in the one-on-one online interviews. Youth received a Qualtrics survey link
258 during the Zoom one-on-one meeting and were asked to complete the survey on their own. We
259 tested the total time spent on the survey and asked the youth some questions to get insights about
260 children's thoughts and feelings as they examined the survey questions. In addition, we shared
261 the survey with additional colleagues in Chile outside of the authorship team to make sure we
262 were using appropriate language. After the food literacy survey, participants were asked about
263 their food expenditure, if they receive pocket money and how they spend it. The survey ended
264 with information on children's and adolescents' demographic characteristics, including age and
265 biological sex. We randomly assigned participants to four different versions of the instrument
266 that differed only in the blocks of choices presented in the DCE section. Within each block, we
267 further reordered the presentation of choice tasks to minimize bias associated with ordering
268 effects.

269 To obtain enough variability and estimate robust models, we used the sample size rule of thumb
270 proposed by Hensher et al., (2005) which considers sampling at least 50 youth for each available

271 alternative in the choice set. Considering this, 150 youth should provide adequate variation for
272 the variables of interest (as noted above, our final sample was 329 participants).

273

274 2.3 Statistical approach

275 The method of DCE is based on Lancaster's new demand theory (Lancaster, 1966) and, Random
276 Utility Theory (RUT) (Ben-Akiva & Bierlaire, 2003; McFadden, 1973). The utility (U_{nti})
277 associated with each decision-maker n for alternative i in choice task t is decomposed into
278 deterministic (X_{nti}) and stochastic (ε_{nti}) components

279

$$280 \quad U_{nti} = \beta_n X_{nti} + \varepsilon_{nti}$$

281

282 where X_{nti} is a vector of observed variables, β_n is a vector of individual-specific parameters
283 reflecting the degree of attributes preference and, ε_{nti} is the independent and identically
284 distributed (IID) error term representing the unobserved part of the utility expression.

285 Multinomial (MNL) models are commonly used to analyze DCE data (Hensher et al., 2005). The
286 IID assumption, however, leads to the Independence of Irrelevant Alternatives (IIA), which
287 poses a limitation in practical applications of the model since it does not account for the degree
288 of heterogeneity of participants' preferences (Ben Akiva & Bierlaire, 2003). Therefore, we
289 estimated mixed logit models (Model 1, Model 2a and Model 2b for H1 and H2). In the mixed
290 logit model, the utility function is modified and β varies over decision-makers rather than being
291 fixed and assumes a continuous distribution. We complemented the mixed logit models with
292 latent class logit models. Although this method is data-driven and not hypothesis-driven, the
293 method allows for better behavioral interpretation, and is especially well-suited for exploring

294 response heterogeneity in discrete choice experiments. It models preferences in categories and
295 explains each participant's probability to belong to a mutually exclusive class "c", meaning that
296 utility derives from a certain attribute and is not individual-specific but depends on the
297 unobservable categorical membership to one of the $c = 1, 2 \dots C$ latent classes (Boxall &
298 Adamowicz, 2002). Swait explains the latent class model as the product of the probability of
299 membership in class s times the probability of choosing alternative i , conditional on being in
300 class s , summed over all classes (Swait, 1994),

$$301 \quad P_i = \sum_{s=1}^S P_{i|s} W_s$$

302
303 In latent class models, β are distributed among decision-makers and follow a discrete
304 distribution. The classes or groups are heterogeneous and share common parameters for class
305 members, but each class or group is distinct. The model also determines how the probability of
306 class membership s and heterogeneous preference for the attributes are associated with
307 participant observable characteristics,

$$308 \quad P(\text{membership})_n = \beta_0 + \beta_1 \text{foodliteracy}_n + \beta_2 \text{money}_n + \beta_3 \text{female}_n + \beta_4 \text{age}_n$$

309
310
311 where the dependent variable $P(\text{membership})$ is the probability that participant i is a member
312 of latent class s ($s = 1, 2 \dots S$). The variable foodliteracy_n is the food literacy score (food
313 system domain) for participant i in latent class s . The variable money_n represents if participant i
314 in latent class s receives pocket money. The model also incorporated relevant socio-demographic
315 characteristics to explain class membership. This method allows us to identify different groups of

316 youth considering the different attributes and socio-demographic characteristics included in the
317 model (e.g., younger children who are both environmentally and health conscious).
318 Statistical analyses were conducted in Stata/SE version 17 (College Station, TX, USA) and
319 statistical significance was evaluated at $\alpha = 0.1$, $\alpha = 0.05$ and $\alpha = 0.01$.

320

321 **3. Results**

322 *3.1 Participants' characteristics*

323 From 1,040 youth invited to participate in the study, 329 youth completed the online survey. We
324 excluded those participants who did not respond to all 8 choice tasks, as well as those who
325 consistently chose “neither” option in every task. We found only two cases of straight-lining
326 (e.g., participants who chose “neither” for all choice tasks) and these participants were dropped
327 from the analysis. The final analytical sample was $n=327$.

328 Table 2 shows descriptive information for the sample. Participants were on average 11.7 (SD
329 1.52) years of age and just under half were girls (48.93%). More than half of participants
330 reported receiving pocket money from some family member (68.81%). However, most obtained
331 it only rarely (26.91%) or once a month (25.69%). Looking at food literacy (food systems
332 domain), the average score was 10.62 (SD 2.01) points from a score of 12 points. More
333 information about the mean score for the other food literacy domains can also be found in Table
334 2.

335 *3.2 Mixed logit model*

336 Table 3 summarizes findings from the mixed logit model. For FOP nutrition warning label
337 alternative specifications (i.e., three labels, one label and no label), we observed no significant
338 differences between three and one label (results not shown). Therefore, we conducted the final

339 analyses with only two levels (i.e., presence of label and no label). Coefficients for apple and
340 price were significant at 0.1 and 0.001 alpha levels respectively. Youth prefer apples over
341 cookies as snacks (0.2191, $p = 0.060$) and the price coefficient is negative as expected (-0.0014,
342 $p < 0.000$) indicating that youth are sensitive to price when they choose snacks. In addition to
343 price and apples, the probability of choosing a snack with a FOP eco-label was favorable in this
344 model (0.0804, $p = 0.059$).

345 In Table 4a and Table 4b, we report coefficient estimates for snack choice for youth who receive
346 pocket money and youth who do not receive pocket money respectively (Model 2a and Model
347 2b). Although this was not one of our driving hypotheses, we included this additional analysis by
348 sub-groups to compare to the results reported by Hartmann et al. (2017), who found differences
349 in participants' choices between those who receive vs those who do not receive pocket money.
350 By dividing the sample into two groups, we observe that in both groups, price does predict
351 choice and has a negative sign as expected (-0.0014, $p < 0.000$). When we look at other attributes,
352 we see some differences between groups in this specification. The coefficient for FOP eco-labels
353 is positive for youth who receive pocket money, suggesting that this group prefers snacks with a
354 FOP eco-label (0.1085, $p = 0.038$). On the other hand, the coefficient for apple is positive for
355 youth who do not receive pocket money and indicates a preference for apples over cookies in this
356 group (0.4047, $p = 0.0078$).

357 *3.3 Latent class logit analyses*

358 We fit latent class logit models with different numbers of classes and used two different
359 information criteria to determine the number of latent classes that would best fit our final model:
360 the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) and the Consistent Akaike Information Criterion
361 (CAIC). The BIC and CAIC suggested that the model with five classes was the best fit (smallest

362 value compared to other classes). Thus, the model with five classes was chosen as the final
363 model (Table 5).

364 Utility parameter estimates and standard errors derived from the five-class latent logit model are
365 presented in Table 6. Class membership probability estimates are reported in Table 7.

366 Characteristics that significantly determined class membership probability were age, sex and the
367 receipt of pocket money. Food literacy (food system domain) was insignificant in any class and
368 was not included in the subsequent descriptions.

369 Considering the sign, magnitude and statistical significance of each attribute coefficient, the
370 characteristics of the five distinct classes of snack consumers are summarized below:

371 *Class 1. Environmentally conscious, price-sensitive yogurt avoiders:* The size of the class was
372 28.6% of the sample, making it the largest class observed in our sample. Members in this class
373 valued the environmental sustainability attribute as measured by the eco-label with a preference
374 for packaged snacks with FOP eco-labels. They also strongly avoided yogurt compared to
375 cookies but did not show other product preferences. Lastly, members of this class were sensitive
376 to price. FOP eco-labeling or carbon tax policies on packaged products would likely influence
377 this group.

378 *Class 2. Young healthy attribute seekers:* With a class size of 26.3% of the sample, members in
379 this class were younger youth. They strongly preferred items with no FOP nutrition warning
380 labels and healthier items such as yogurt and apples over cookies. Members of this class were
381 clearly the group that was more sensitive to interventions such as the LFLA implemented in
382 Chile. These participants did not choose snacks based on the environmental sustainability
383 attribute or prices suggesting nutrition and health-related attributes were more important to them.

384 *Class 3. Price-sensitive cookie lovers:* This was the smallest class: 10.3% of the sample. This
385 class consisted of youth who loved cookies and would prefer them over yogurt or apples as a
386 snack. Members in this class were also price sensitive. Compared to other classes, this class was
387 the least sensitive to the price attribute. In addition, youth in this group usually received pocket
388 money (Table 7). This characteristic suggests they have better budgeting skills compared to
389 youth in other classes. Youth in this class could respond to taxes on unhealthy foods and
390 beverages but the magnitude of their response might be limited because of the low-price
391 sensitivity.

392 *Class 4. Healthy snack bargain buyers:* Members of this class (11.8% of the sample) were
393 mostly girls and preferred healthier snacks such as yogurt or apple over cookies. Compared to
394 other classes, members in this class were moderately sensitive to the price attribute. In addition,
395 youth in this class seemed to value FOP nutrition warning labels displayed on a food package but
396 not eco-labels. Regarding policy interventions, this class could benefit from interventions such as
397 the LFLA implemented in Chile complemented with healthy subsidies targeted to fruits,
398 vegetables, and dairy.

399 *Class 5. Environmentally conscious, price-sensitive, cookie lovers:* In this class (23% of the
400 sample), the probability of selecting a snack was greatly influenced by price. Youth in this class
401 strongly prefer cookies over yogurt or apple as a snack and valued the environmental
402 sustainability attribute (eco-label) on a packaged product. In addition, youth in this class were the
403 most sensitive to prices compared to other classes. This group could respond well to taxes on
404 unhealthy foods and beverages because of the price sensitivity. However, the response could be
405 limited because youth in this group usually do not receive pocket money. Lastly, members of
406 this class would benefit from FOP eco-labeling policies on packaged products, but other

407 complementary interventions would be needed to increase health awareness and avoid
408 unintended consequences of eco-labels such as the halo effect.

409

410 **4. Discussion**

411 Using a DCE framework, this novel study evaluated motivations of youth's purchasing behavior
412 by assessing different food attributes that shape snack choice. To our knowledge, this study is the
413 first experimental study conducted with Chilean youth that assessed the interacting effects of
414 food attributes including price, FOP nutrition warning labels, FOP eco-labels and product type.
415 The experimental approach in this study is novel because only a few DCEs reported in the
416 literature focus on healthy food choices in children (Michaels-Igbokwe et al., 2021;
417 Rusmevichientong et al., 2021; Rigo et al., 2023; Landwehr et al., 2023). In our study, we found
418 that youth's purchasing behavior is mostly determined by price, followed by product type and
419 environmental sustainability as measured by the FOP eco-label.

420 H1: "The presence of the (1a) FOP warning label changes the likelihood of choosing a snack",
421 was not supported by the mixed logit models. Contrary to FOP eco-labels, FOP nutrition warning
422 labels did not influence youth purchase behavior in our sample (non-significant results). These
423 results differ from what Cash et al. found in a sample of Canadian children aged 8-12 – namely,
424 that they would avoid food products with traffic-light warning labels (Cash et al., 2017).

425 Previous studies have reported that the initial implementation of the LFLA changed food
426 purchase behaviors; however, these analyses were not disaggregated by age group (Smith Taillie
427 et al., 2022). Youth's response to the FOP nutrition warning labels might be more resistant than
428 adults' responses, or they might have become habituated to seeing labels on packaged foods after
429 repeated exposure to them for over eight years now. Similarly, a recent qualitative study with

430 mothers of children (2-14 years old) found that mothers experienced “labels’ fatigue” but at the
431 same time, they showed more awareness about nutrition issues and valued natural foods (Correa
432 et al., 2022). To maintain the initial effect of the warning labels, the government should revisit
433 the educational campaigns conducted at the initial implementation of the law and reinforce the
434 message that when making food choices, fewer labels are better. This should be emphasized in
435 schools, as they have played a key role as promoters of Chile’s law, which was lost during the
436 COVID-19 pandemic. Interestingly, and in line with Correa et al., participants in our study
437 preferred apples to cookies in all models which could indicate more awareness about nutrition.
438 Our findings are also consistent with an experimental study conducted in Peru in a sample of 449
439 youth (10-14 years old) from public schools where authors reported that FOP nutrition warning
440 labels did not influence purchase intention (Saavedra-García et al., 2022). Nevertheless, in the
441 latent profile analyses, we identified a large group of “healthy attribute seekers” (26.3%) who
442 preferred healthier items without FOP nutrition warning labels. We acknowledge the inclusion of
443 food that did not carry any warning labels (i.e., apple), which could have influenced the low
444 importance youth provided to the warning label attribute and highlighted the importance of the
445 eco-label. We made this intentional tradeoff in the design to make it more realistic and less
446 complex for youth. Apple was included because it was mentioned as one of the top favorite
447 snacks in the focus group discussions conducted to elicit the attributes and attribute levels to be
448 included in the experiment (Fretes et al., 2021).

449 Another important finding derived from the mixed logit models was the preference for snacks
450 with eco-labels. H1: “The presence of the (1b) eco-label label changes the likelihood of choosing
451 a snack”, was supported by the models. In a previous qualitative study, we reported that children
452 showed some level of awareness about the impact of their behaviors on the environment (Fretes

453 et al., 2021). With the DCE results, we observe that youth’s awareness of environmental
454 sustainability is translated into their purchasing behavior by significantly valuing items with a
455 simple FOP eco-label that reads “I take care of the planet”. In addition, we observed two classes
456 of environmentally conscious youth in the latent class analysis which make up 52% of the
457 sample. However, H3: “Higher food literacy scores (food system domain) change the likelihood
458 of choosing a snack with an eco-label” was not supported by the latent class models (Table 7).
459 Testing of this hypothesis was complicated in part by the marginal performance of the translated
460 food systems knowledge scale, which had not previously been validated for Spanish-speaking
461 youth. More work is needed to understand if food literacy does predict youth choices in the
462 context of sustainability. In the past years, youth have been actively participating in global
463 youth-led climate strikes, asking governments to act on climate change and demanding political
464 action on healthy sustainable diets (Trewern et al., 2021). Young people may be more anxious
465 about the effects of climate disasters in their future (Clayton & Karazsia, 2020) and therefore, be
466 more sensitive to FOP eco-labels. Our results contradict findings from a recent systematic review
467 that assessed consumers’ perceptions of food-related sustainability (van Bussel et al., 2022).
468 Authors found that sustainability did not yet influence consumers’ food choices. Yet, most
469 studies included in the review were conducted in adults from high-income countries. A note of
470 concern, however, is that environmentally conscious youth in our sample typically preferred less
471 healthy snacks (i.e., sugared cookies), suggesting a possible tension between environmental
472 sustainability and nutrition. Lastly, in some products shown to youth in our study, the size of the
473 eco-label was greater than that of the warning labels, which may have influenced the results
474 obtained.

475 The mixed logit models supported H2: “Price affects youth’s demand for snack foods”. Our
476 findings reveal that price was the most important determinant of youth’s snack choice. This
477 result remained consistent across all models as well as when we conducted analyses by groups
478 (those that receive versus those that do not receive pocket money). In all cases, we obtained a
479 negative coefficient indicating youth are less likely to choose snacks with higher prices, which is
480 as expected (Cash et al., 2017). Hartmann et al., in contrast, depicted a more heterogeneous
481 picture and reported that youth who received pocket money preferred snacks with lower prices
482 while those who did not receive pocket money exhibited the opposite behavior with a preference
483 for snacks with higher prices (Hartmann et al., 2017). The more homogenous picture in our study
484 might be a result of youth coming from low- and middle-income neighborhoods and being
485 equipped with better budgeting skills considering exposure to scarcity situations at the household
486 level, independent on receiving or not pocket money.

487 Regarding the different types of products presented in the DCE, apples were preferred over
488 cookies in most models. Preference for this snack could be a result of social desirability bias,
489 and/or the fact that participants in this study were siblings of participants in two nutrition
490 cohorts. Interestingly, our food literacy measure did not predict differences in youth’s snack
491 choice. When we analyzed youth’s individual characteristics and the probability of class
492 membership, we found that only age, sex and receiving (or not) pocket money were associated
493 with class membership. This finding could be because our study sample was fairly homogeneous
494 in terms of demographic characteristics: participants were from low- and middle-income
495 neighborhoods in Santiago, Chile. Future research could evaluate more heterogeneous samples in
496 terms of household income level, type of school and proximity to corner stores in neighborhoods,
497 factors that could have an influence on purchasing behavior and food literacy.

498 A strength of this study is the use of a mixed methods approach to validate the attributes and
499 attribute levels to be included in the DCE. In addition, relatively few studies have documented
500 youth attitudes and preferences for environmental sustainability attributes such as an eco-label
501 (e.g., de Brabandere et al, 2022; Fretes et al, 2021; Hong, et al. 2024), and, to our knowledge,
502 none before ours have used a discrete choice framework to test youth responses to such labels
503 along with other food attributes. Therefore, our study findings are relevant for future policies that
504 consider environmental sustainability along with nutrition and health-related food attributes. This
505 study, however, is not without limitations. First, youth in the sample were from low and middle-
506 income neighborhoods in southeastern Santiago, Chile. Hence, findings from this study may not
507 be representative of all 10-14-year-old youth in Chile, and care should be taken in how the
508 results are interpreted. Second, hypothetical bias could exist given the nature of stated preference
509 methods such as DCE. In our study, youth were not compelled to purchase the selected snack,
510 and this could have influenced their selections. An important additional consideration is that our
511 study was conducted during the COVID-19 pandemic (June-September 2021), when there were
512 still strict lockdowns and a noticeable economic crisis in the country that could have influenced
513 youth preferences. Also, we did not include brand as an attribute as it was not the objective of
514 this work to separate out the effect of brand and product type and this omission could have
515 influenced the results. Future studies could be conducted in “real-world” environments such as
516 schools or corner stores using incentive-compatible methods to account for hypothetical bias.
517 Incentives in the form of compensation can be framed as rewards to emphasize that the money
518 participants are going to spend in the DCE is their own money. Yet, our findings provide a better
519 understanding of youth as autonomous consumers in an evolving policy environment.
520

521 **5. Conclusion**

522 When we refer to consumers, we usually think about adults. Youth as autonomous consumers
523 were not typically objects of investigation until recent years. Therefore, it is still not well
524 understood how youth behave as decision-makers in commercial environments for food. Results
525 from this study are a novel contribution to fill this research gap by highlighting Chilean youth's
526 purchasing behavior and the value they give to different food attributes. We used a mixed-
527 methods approach and had the opportunity to listen to children's and adolescents' voices and
528 opinions about food, nutrition, and environmental sustainability, with a particular focus on eco-
529 labeling and sustainability messaging.

530 While our results provide evidence that children are responsive to eco-labels when making
531 autonomous food purchase decisions, this alone does not ensure that such approaches will be
532 successful drivers of more sustainable food changes. Indeed, our study only hints at some of the
533 key challenges facing researchers, policymakers and food industry professionals when
534 considering the design of coherent messaging – i.e., messages that clearly communicate
535 environmental and nutrition and health attributes of a product across a variety of settings and
536 products – to describe environmental sustainability and nutrition and health related food
537 attributes on packaged foods. However, it is important to consider potential tensions between
538 sustainability and nutrition that may be faced by consumers, such as we do in our design here.
539 Moreover, these tensions are important considerations for both assessment and guidance as the
540 research community continues to work on standardized metrics to assess both aspects of diets.
541 Future youth-facing work could evaluate different eco-label prototypes to assess their
542 performance in terms of visual design, ease of understanding in the food choice context and the
543 extent to which the eco-label influences purchasing behavior in a real-world scenario. Which

544 footprint calculation methods (e.g., carbon, nitrogen, water footprints) are better to inform eco-
545 labeling also still remain unclear.

546 Considering youth as key stakeholders in the food system and their timely call to action for
547 healthy, sustainable diets, this study highlights the importance to bring youth's voices to the table
548 when discussing consumer-oriented strategies to make diets healthier and sustainable. Youth are
549 current consumers, influencers, and future consumers. Although policy change and its impacts
550 on human and planetary health outcomes can take time to occur, policy makers should consider
551 improving child and adolescent diets a priority in their agendas given the significant economic,
552 social, and environmental impacts food choices can have both for consumers and for the planet.

553 Results from this research call for a systems approach to improving nutrition and health
554 outcomes in youth, where the food system plays an important role in delivering nutritious, safe,
555 affordable, and sustainable diets. Policies should be designed in a way that stimulate
556 interdependent actions across different parts of the food system, from food supply chains and
557 production to consumer preferences, involving multiple stakeholders. With the innovation
558 around food labeling in Chile, the co-occurrence of eco-labels and FOP warning labels in food
559 products provides an opportunity to change manufacturers and consumers' behavior toward
560 healthier and more sustainable food choices.

561

562 **Data availability**

563 The datasets generated and/or analyzed during the current study are not publicly available but are
564 available from the corresponding author on reasonable request.

565

566 **Declaration of Interest**

567 None.

568

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585

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Table 1. Choice experiment design: Product attributes and attribute levels

Attributes	Levels
Product type	1. Yogurt 2. Apple 3. Cookies
Front-of-pack nutrition warning label	1. One label 2. Three labels 3. No label
Front-of-pack eco label	1. Yes 2. No
Price	1. 400 Chilean pesos 2. 500 Chilean pesos 3. 600 Chilean pesos 4. 800 Chilean pesos

Table 2. Participants' characteristics, 2021 (n=327)

Characteristics	n=327 Frequency	%
Biological sex		
Girl	160	48.93
Boy	155	47.40
Prefer not to say	12	3.67
Age		
10 years	110	33.64
11 years	51	15.60
12 years	54	16.51
13 years	52	15.90
14 years	60	18.35
Age, years (mean, SD)	11.70	1.52
Get pocket money		
Yes	225	68.81
No	102	31.19
Frequency pocket money		
Never	102	31.19
Rarely	88	26.91
Once a month	84	25.69
Once a week	39	11.93
Once a day	13	3.98
Amount pocket money		
100 or less	49	14.98
200 – 500	104	31.80
600 – 1.500	31	9.48
1,600 – More than 2,000	40	12.23
Food literacy score (mean, SD)	33.18	4.30
Food systems knowledge	10.62	2.01
Cooking skills	2.11	0.94
Cooking knowledge	5.30	0.85
Nutrition knowledge	11.69	2.18
Self-efficacy	3.48	0.96

Notes: Food literacy score maximum score is 40 points. The maximum scores for each section are food systems knowledge=12 points, cooking skills=3 points, cooking knowledge=6 points, nutrition knowledge=15 points, and self-efficacy=4 points.

Table 3. Mixed logit choice model (Model 1, base model)

Attributes	β	SE	95% CI	p-value
Product type				
Cookies	Ref			
Apple	0.2191*	0.1167	-0.0096, 0.4475	0.060
Yogurt	0.0241	0.0917	-0.1557, 0.2039	0.793
Neither	-2.2711***	0.1696	-2.6037, -1.9385	0.000
FOP nutrition warning label	-0.0579	0.0519	-0.1595, 0.0437	0.264
FOP eco-label	0.0804*	0.0425	-0.0029, 0.1638	0.059
Price	-0.0014***	0.0002	-0.0017, -0.0011	0.000
Observations	7,848			
Number of participants	327			
χ^2	284.83			
χ^2 (p-value)	0.000			
Log likelihood	-2,436.92			

Notes: Observations = number of participants x 8 choice sets x 3 alternatives/choice set.

*p<0.1; ** p<0.05; *** p<0.01

Table 4a. Mixed logit choice model (Model 2a: for subsample receiving pocket money)

Attributes	β	SE	95% CI	p-value
Product type				
Cookies	Ref			
Apple	0.1458	0.1349	-0.1185, 0.4101	0.280
Yogurt	0.0921	0.1093	-0.1217, 0.3066	0.399
Neither	-2.3541***	0.2076	-2.7610, -1.9471	0.000
FOP nutrition warning label	-0.0531	0.0622	-0.1750, 0.0688	0.393
FOP eco-label	0.1085**	0.0523	-0.0058, 0.2111	0.038
Price	-0.0014***	0.0002	-0.0018, -0.0010	0.000
Observations	5,400			
Number of participants	225			
χ^2	197			
χ^2 (p-value)	0.000			
Log likelihood	-1,653.43			

Notes: Observations = number of participants who receive pocket money x 8 choice sets x 3 alternatives/choice set.

*p<0.1; ** p<0.05; *** p<0.01

Table 4b. Mixed logit choice model (Model 2b: for subsample not receiving pocket money)

Attributes	β	SE	95% CI	p-value
Product type				
Cookies	Ref			
Apple	0.4047*	0.2298	-0.0457, 0.8551	0.078
Yogurt	-0.1369	0.1701	-0.4703, 0.1966	0.421
Neither	-2.1410***	0.2997	-2.7283, -1.5536	0.000
FOP nutrition warning label	-0.0739	0.0947	-0.2597, 0.1118	0.435
FOP eco-label	-0.0126	0.0747	-0.1589, 0.1337	0.866
Price	-0.0014***	0.0003	-0.0020, -0.0008	0.000
Observations	2,448			
Number of participants	102			
χ^2	95.64			
χ^2 (p-value)	0.000			
Log likelihood	-775.28			

Notes: Observations = number of participants who do not receive pocket money x 8 choice sets x 3 alternatives/choice set.

*p<0.1; ** p<0.05; *** p<0.01

Table 5. Information criteria to determine the optimum number of latent classes

Classes	Log likelihood	BIC	CAIC
2	-2040.0	4178.9	4195.9
3	-1871.5	3905.2	3933.2
4	-1804.0	3833.8	3872.9
5	-1753.6	3796.6	3846.6
6	-1723.8	3800.9	3861.9

Table 6. Latent class model utility parameter estimates and class size

Variable	Classes				
	1	2	3	4	5
Price	-0.0038*** (0.0004)	-3.58e-05 (0.0006)	-0.0043** (0.0019)	-0.0032*** (-0.0008)	-0.0017** (0.0007)
Warning label	-0.1663 (0.1197)	-0.9513*** (0.3198)	0.4992 (0.5443)	-0.5710* (0.3349)	0.4613 (0.5787)
Ecolabel	0.2861** (0.1180)	0.2615 (0.2323)	-0.2354 (0.6556)	0.1793 (0.2665)	0.5876* (0.6497)
Yogurt	-0.4896*** (0.1267)	3.0900*** (0.3273)	-3.6863*** (0.7727)	0.7771** (0.3673)	-3.8197*** (0.6685)
Apple	-0.2097 (0.2385)	3.1909*** (0.3417)	-1.2515** (0.5899)	2.1633*** (0.5670)	-3.1273*** (0.4455)
Neither	-4.8399*** (0.3524)	-0.4617 (0.4668)	-3.9616*** (1.2044)	0.0125 (0.6417)	-5.4675*** (0.6702)
Class size	28.6%	26.3%	10.3%	11.8%	23.0%

***p<0.01 **p<0.05 *p<0.1. Standard errors presented in parenthesis.

Class 1 = Environmentally conscious, price sensitive yogurt avoiders; Class 2 = Young healthy attribute seekers; Class 3: Price sensitive cookie lovers; Class 4 = Healthy snack bargain buyers; Class 5 = Environmentally conscious, price sensitive, cookie lovers.

Table 7. Latent class model membership probability estimates-Model with food system knowledge

Variable	Classes			
	1	2	3	4
Age	0.0578 (0.1155)	-0.2272* (0.1159)	-0.1594 (0.1798)	-0.0161 (0.1463)
Sex				
Boy	Ref	Ref	Ref	Ref
Girl	0.3248 (0.3656)	0.0898 (0.3556)	0.6801 (0.5729)	1.6410*** (0.5337)
Prefer not to say	0.7321 (1.4544)	0.4855 (1.3061)	1.4535 (1.5675)	3.1671** (1.2538)
Pocket money	0.2108 (0.3761)	-0.0069 (0.3589)	2.0462* (1.0577)	0.0522 (0.4747)
Food system knowledge	0.1180 (0.0835)	0.0333 (0.0767)	0.0297 (0.1139)	0.1332 (0.1100)
Constant	-1.8118 (1.6808)	2.4429 (1.5932)	-1.5972 (2.5989)	-2.9947 (2.1048)
Observations	7,848			
Log-likelihood	-1753.09			

***p<0.01 **p<0.05 *p<0.1. Standard errors presented in parenthesis. Class 5 is the reference group.

Appendices

Appendix A. Supplementary tables

Table S1. Latent profile attribute coefficients with standard errors + class size. Model with nutrition knowledge and food systems knowledge dimensions

Variable	Classes				
	1	2	3	4	5
Price	-0.0038*** (0.0004)	-0.0001 (0.0006)	-0.0017** (0.0007)	-0.0031*** (0.0008)	-0.0011 (0.0021)
Warning label	-0.1648 (0.1170)	-0.8470*** (0.2909)	0.4675 (0.5522)	-0.4619 (0.3446)	-1.0451 (1.0565)
Ecolabel	0.3052*** (0.1122)	0.2309 (0.2257)	0.6005* (0.3321)	0.2612 (0.2663)	-0.5249 (0.9027)
Yogurt	-0.4283*** (0.1225)	2.9991*** (0.3053)	-3.8464*** (0.6487)	0.9147** (0.3579)	29.2461 (6731.37)
Apple	-0.2834 (0.2124)	3.1773*** (0.3369)	-3.0811*** (0.4497)	2.2839*** (0.5613)	-2.0008** (0.8639)
Class size	28.6%	26.3%	10.3%	11.8%	23.0%

***p<0.01 **p<0.05 *p<0.1

Table S2. Latent profile model class membership probability estimates-Model with nutrition knowledge and food systems knowledge dimensions

Variable	Classes			
	1	2	3	4
Age	0.2680 (0.1832)	-0.0209 (0.1902)	0.2144 (0.1904)	.1950 .2075
Sex				
Boy	Ref	Ref	Ref	Ref
Girl	-0.5601 (0.5869)	-0.7430 (0.6059)	-0.7988 (0.6094)	0.8221 (0.7282)
Prefer not to say	-0.9307 (1.3485)	-1.2279 (1.4042)	-1.7761 (1.6130)	1.4499 (1.3632)
Pocket money	-1.8045 (1.1088)	-2.0813* (1.1198)	-2.0205* (1.1159)	-2.0208* (1.1469)
Nutrition knowledge	0.1391 (0.1347)	0.1909 (0.1455)	0.0568 (0.1370)	0.2613 (0.1649)
Food systems knowledge	0.0755 (0.1286)	-0.0371 (0.1307)	-0.0167 (0.1293)	0.0508 (0.1484)
Constant	0.5194 (2.3362)	3.9186 (2.3937)	0.9515 (2.4137)	-0.5785 (2.6253)
Observations	7,848			
Log-likelihood	-1751.55			

***p<0.01 **p<0.05 *p<0.1. Standard errors presented in parenthesis. Class 5 if the reference group.

Table S3. Food literacy scale validity (internal consistency) (n=327)

Questions	Correlation item-test	Correlation item-rest	Cronbach-a coefficient
Domain 1: Food systems concepts			
<i>Part I</i>			
1. Which of the following things are not needed for a fruit or vegetable to grow?	0.3749	0.1792	0.6013
2. Draw a line to match each vegetable to the plant part it comes from (Broccoli-Flowers)	0.1930	-0.0341	0.6417
3. Draw a line to match each vegetable to the plant part it comes from (Carrot-Root)	0.5594	0.3828	0.5483
4. Draw a line to match each vegetable to the plant part it comes from (Spinach-Leaves)	0.5108	0.3178	0.5647
5. Draw a line to match each food to the animal that it comes from (Honey-Bees)	0.4155	0.2316	0.5796
6. Draw a line to match each food to the animal that it comes from (Cheese-Cows)	0.4219	0.2387	0.5779
7. Draw a line to match each food to the animal that it comes from (Bacon-Pigs)	Constant	Constant	Constant
<i>Part II</i>			
8. Draw a line to match steps 1-5 to the picture that describes each step (Step 1-A hen lays an egg at a farm)	0.3869	0.1497	0.6005
9. Draw a line to match steps 1-5 to the picture that describes each step (Step 2-The eggs are washed and packaged in a carton)	0.4233	0.2233	0.5802
10. Draw a line to match steps 1-5 to the picture that describes each step (Step 3-The carton of eggs travels to the store or market)	0.6675	0.5224	0.5177
11. Draw a line to match steps 1-5 to the picture that describes each step (Step 4-Isidora or a family member purchases the eggs)	0.6205	0.4549	0.5320
12. Draw a line to match steps 1-5 to the picture that describes each step (Step 5- Isidora or someone in the family cooks the egg to eat)	0.4127	0.1981	0.5836
<i>Total scale</i>			0.6003
Domain 2: Cooking skills			
1. I can use a knife to cut up food into smaller pieces	0.7180	0.3269	0.3204
2. I can crack an egg into a bowl	0.6724	0.2549	0.4452
3. I can use a measuring cup to measure ingredients	0.7049	0.3056	0.3582
<i>Total scale</i>			0.4751
Domain 3: Cooking knowledge			
1. Which kitchen tool picks up hot food safely	0.4437	0.0927	0.2435
2. Which kitchen tool removes skin from fruit or vegetable	0.4117	0.0507	0.2711
3. Which kitchen tool rinses food and drains liquid from solid food	0.4972	0.1291	0.2032
4. To make sure that the foods we eat are safe, which of the following should be clean before cooking?	0.4805	0.1354	0.2087
	0.4619	0.1120	0.2246

<p>5. Some foods are only safe to eat if they have been cooked first. Circle all of the food that should be cooked first before eating</p> <p>6. True or false. When preparing meals, raw meats should not touch other foods like salad or fruit until the raw meat has been cooked</p> <p><i>Total scale</i></p>	0.4749	0.1262	0.2162
<p>Domain 4: Nutrition knowledge</p> <p><i>Part 1</i></p> <p>1. Circle the option that would make the healthiest meal (main meal)</p> <p>2. Circle the option that would make the healthiest meal (side dish)</p> <p>3. Circle the option that would make the healthiest meal (dessert)</p> <p>4. Which snack would be the healthiest for Joaquin to choose?</p> <p>5. Which would be the healthiest drink to order?</p> <p><i>Part 2</i></p> <p>6. A box of cereal has a lot of information and pictures on it. Where on the box would you find the best source of information about how healthy the food is?</p> <p>7. It is recommended that you eat foods that are low in sugar. Based on the warning labels of two different cookies shown below, circle which one is lower in sugar</p> <p>8. Circle the best answer. The energy you get from eating healthy foods helps you to...</p> <p>9. Please draw a line to match each food with their food group (Banana-Fruit)</p> <p>10. Please draw a line to match each food with their food group (Grilled chicken-Protein)</p> <p>11. Please draw a line to match each food with their food group (Green beans-Vegetable)</p> <p>12. Please draw a line to match each food with their food group (Whole wheat bread-Grain)</p> <p>13. Please draw a line to match each food with their food group (Cheese-Dairy)</p> <p>14. Please draw a line to match each food with their food group (Fruit flavored candy-Does not fit in a food group)</p> <p>15. Do you know how many servings of fruits and vegetables you should eat daily to stay healthy?</p> <p><i>Total scale</i></p>	<p>Constant</p> <p>0.3126</p> <p>0.3315</p> <p>0.2110</p> <p>0.2312</p> <p>0.2844</p> <p>0.2221</p> <p>0.3518</p> <p>0.4132</p> <p>0.5200</p> <p>0.3949</p> <p>0.4307</p> <p>0.2637</p> <p>0.4738</p> <p>0.3222</p>	<p>Constant</p> <p>0.1084</p> <p>0.1286</p> <p>0.0000</p> <p>0.0204</p> <p>0.0724</p> <p>0.0022</p> <p>0.1452</p> <p>0.2101</p> <p>0.3309</p> <p>0.1823</p> <p>0.2311</p> <p>0.0371</p> <p>0.2675</p> <p>0.1163</p>	<p>Constant</p> <p>0.3808</p> <p>0.3744</p> <p>0.4171</p> <p>0.4087</p> <p>0.3894</p> <p>0.4142</p> <p>0.3679</p> <p>0.3503</p> <p>0.3104</p> <p>0.3564</p> <p>0.3423</p> <p>0.4022</p> <p>0.3303</p> <p>0.3798</p> <p>0.3920</p>
<p>Domain 5: Self-efficacy regarding eating</p> <p>1. For meals and snacks at home I can try a vegetable that an adult serves me</p> <p>2. For meals and snacks at home I can try a fruit that an adult serves me</p> <p>3. When eating lunch with a friend I can eat a fruit even if my friend is not</p> <p>4. When eating lunch with a friend I can eat vegetables even if my friend says they are “yucky”</p> <p><i>Total scale</i></p>	<p>0.6935</p> <p>0.6806</p> <p>0.7518</p> <p>0.7037</p>	<p>0.4266</p> <p>0.4084</p> <p>0.5170</p> <p>0.4420</p>	<p>0.6147</p> <p>0.6265</p> <p>0.5529</p> <p>0.6044</p> <p>0.6671</p>

Appendix B. Supplementary figure

Figure S1. Examples of snacks used in the choice experiment

